

Archaeological Explorations in Charkhi-Dadri-2 block, District Bhiwani, Haryana

Vivek Dangi

Department of History

A.I. Jat H. M. P.G. College, Rohtak, Haryana

Parveen Kumar

Department of A.I.H.Culture and Archaeology

Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra, Haryana

Abstract

This paper is a preliminary report of village-to-village survey of Charkhi-Dadri Block-2 of Bhiwani district, Haryana. During August-September 2011 a total of 59 sites were documented. This venture aims to understand relationship between the Ganeshwar-Jodhapura culture and Harappan Civilization, besides the expansion of Harappan civilization in South-western fringe of the Ghaggar plains and to give general information about the archaeological sites in the region. The result of this survey will address a number of problems such of size of the settlements, geo-coordinates etc.

Introduction

Ghaggar plains are very important for the study of rise and fall of Harappan civilization. High density of Harappan settlements and study of settlement patterns (Kumar 2009, Dangi 2010) shows it was the core area of Harappan civilization. Fertile land and availability of water provided agriculture surplus which might have played important role in urbanization during third millennium BCE in the area. The study area lies in the southern fringe of the Ghaggar plain (Fig 1) which is marked by the presence of Aravalli hills and expansion of the Great Indian desert. The area is rich in archaeological remains and the fact it has been proved by the explorations and excavations conducted by various scholars. The credit for initiating archaeological field work goes to Suraj Bhan (1972, 1975). Thereafter Rajiv Joon of the M.D. University, Rohtak conducted explorations and reported some sites of various periods (Rajiv 1997). With this archaeological background, village-to-village survey was carried out in the Dadri Block-2 of Bhiwani district, Haryana.

Topography and drainage system

The area is a part of the Ghaggar plain and its southern and western portions are marked by a sluggish transition to the Thar desert. The topography of the region owes its existence to geomorphic processes having closer affinity to the arid climate, both in the recent and past geologic periods. The dominating features of the topography are the Aeolian deposits of various shapes and thickness overlying the Pleistocene alluvium that can be observed in the northern portion of the study area. The area under present study prairie plain except some detached peaks of the Aravalli range. The highest hill of this range is known as Kaliana peak (1470 feet).

Dohan is the only seasonal stream in the study area. It originates in Ghoghu and Bhagaur villages near Jaipur, Rajasthan and passes through villages such as Palari, Jawa, Jhojhu Kalan, Balali, Kaliana and disappear in the sand dunes near village Kaliwas. In 1882 and 1885 this stream caused huge flood in the area. After 1947 no water has been seen in the stream and the channel disappeared now days because of cultivation.

Mineral Resources

Ghaggar plains are not very rich in mineral resources. But at a few places following mineral resources are available:

Iron ore: In the Kaliana hills at numerous places lenses of iron ore, mainly magnetite are found (Haryana district Gazetteers, Bhiwani 1982: 15). At a number of places heaps of slag were noticed during explorations, indicating that the iron was produced.

Copper: In the northern side of the study area near Tosham hills copper deposits are reported (Grover and Kumar 1980).

Glass Sand: Quartzities are found in the area around village Atela Kakan and Atela Khurd. This can be used for manufacturing window glass and bottle glass (Haryana district Gazetteers, Bhiwani 1982: 15).

Flexible sandstone: This type of sand stone is very rare as it is flexible like plastic. The only source of this type of stone in India is in Kaliaana hills. A band of about 2-3 feet thick is located along with southern ridge of Kaliaana hill (Haryana district Gazetteers, Bhiwani 1982: 16). Authors collected some samples from the hill.

Methodology

- 1) The present researcher conducted an extensive village-to-village survey in the region using topographic maps.
- 2) A GPS handset (Garmin, GPSmap 60CSx) was used to record correct co-ordinates of the sites.
- 3) Proper sampling of the pottery and other remains from the surface and exposed sections was done.
- 4) On the basis of ecological conditions and detailed analysis of the ancient settlements, different categories of the sites like regional centers, villages, industrial centers and camp sites have been identified. The main emphasis was laid on locating sites and on observing the distribution pattern of the cultural remains in the area. The date of the sites was decided on the basis of occurrence of diagnostic ceramic shapes of ancient cultures. The estimation about the size of the sites was made on the basis of the area, up to which cultural deposit was found.
- 5) Cultural material discovered from the survey and housed in different museums was analyzed and studied to address the problems.
- 6) The available published literature and survey reports including unpublished dissertations were examined and their data was also included in this study. Following table 1 is the list of sites explored by researchers :

Table 1 Showing explored sites along with geo-references, previous work and cultural sequence (Fig 2).

Sr. No	Site Name	Lat.	Long.	Size in Hectare	Previous work	Cultural Sequence
1	Akhtiarpur	28 37 59.7	76 11 01.7	2	New	Hist, Med
2	Assawari	28 33 16.2	76 08 50.3	1	Rajiv 1997: 12	LH, Hist
3	Atela Kalan	28 35 34.5	76 06 40.3	2	New	Hist,
4	Badal	28 32 33.3	76 07 38.8	6	New	Med
5	Badhwana	28 29 02.6	76 11 22.0	2	New	Hist, Med
6	Balali-1	28 30 09.5	76 10 37.9	1	New	Med
7	Balali-2	28 30 36.9	76 10 40.8	2	New	Hist, Med
8	Balali-3	28 30 31.4	76 10 13.2	2	Rajiv 1997: 14	Hist, Med
9	Balrad	28 27 16.3	76 12 47.6	1	New	Hist, Med
10	Barsana-1	28 34 53.3	76 07 26.6	3	Rajiv 1997: 13	LH, Med
11	Barsana-2	28 35 43.5	76 07 35.8	1	New	Hist, Med
12	Bhiri-Kalan	28 36 05.6	76 09 21.2	2	New	Hist, Med
13	Bhiri-Khurd	28 36 31.1	76 09 42.4	3	New	Hist, Med
14	Bijana-1	28 27 58.9	76 08 45.3	1	Rajiv 1997: 13	LH, Hist
15	Bijana-2	28 27 18.7	76 08 00.7	2	New	LH
16	Chandani	28 28 45.4	76 07 19.7	1	Rajiv 1997: 17	Med
17	Chappar -2	28 38 03.7	76 06 14.5	2	Rajiv 1997: 15	Med
18	Chappar-1	28 37 15.2	76 06 20.6	1	Rajiv 1997: 15	Hist, Med
19	Charkhi-1	28 35 32.4	76 12 58.7	1	Rajiv 1997: 15-16	Hist, Med
20	Charkhi-2	28 37 10.8	76 13 10.2	2	New	LH, Hist
21	Chirya	28 27 31.8	76 17 22.7	1	Rajiv 1997: 16	Hist, Med
22	Dadhibana Chillar-1	28 29 58.2	76 13 49.4	1	Rajiv 1997: 19-20	LH, Hist, Med
23	Dadhibana Chillar-2	28 29 46.2	76 13 12.4	1	New	LH
24	Dadhibana-1	28 30 10.8	76 12 24.0	1	New	Hist, Med
25	Dadhibana-2	28 29 58.5	76 11 58.6	1	Rajiv 1997: 18	Hist, Med
26	Datoli	28 27 58.5	76 14 33.1	-	Rajiv 1997: 19	Hist, Med

27	Dhauki-1	28 40 01.3	76.09.48.5	3	Rajiv 1997: 17	EH, MH, LH, Hist
28	Dhauki-2	28 39 19.0	76 09 43.4	3	New	LH, Hist
29	Dhikara	28 38 33.3	76 15 16.7	1	Rajiv 1997: 20	Hist
30	Dudhwa	28 28 57.6	76 13 39.3	1	Rajiv 1997: 18-19	Hist, Med
31	Fatehgrh	28 39 12.0	76 13 14.4	-	New	Hist, Med
32	Gudana	28 31 09.2	76 06 28.1	3	New	Hist, Med
33	Jawa-1	28 28 15.3	76 09 37.5	1	Rajiv 1997: 21	Med
34	Jawa-2	28 28 05.6	76 09 17.9	1	New	Hist
35	Jhojhu Kalan-1	28 31 10.0	76 09 54.5	1	Rajiv 1997: 20	Med
36	Jhojhu Kalan-2	28 32 11.3	76 08 40.7	1	New	Hist, Med
37	Kalali	28 31 38.4	76 10 35.1	1	Rajiv 1997: 22	Hist, Med
38	Kaliana-1	28 33 27.7	76 12 25.9	2	Rajiv 1997: 22	Hist
39	Kaliana-2	28 33 13.4	76 11 45.8	1	Rajiv 1997: 22	Med
40	Kheri Bura	28 35 21.2	76 11 27.7	2	New	Hist, Med
41	Mandola	28 31 10.9	76 12 49.1	2	Rajiv 1997: 24	Hist, Med
42	Mandoli-1	28 32 17.7	76 13 34.7	2	Rajiv 1997: 23-24	Hist, Med
43	Mandoli-2	28 32 01.9	76 13 46.9	3	Rajiv 1997: 24	LH, Med
44	Mankawas-1	28 37 27.1	76 10 36.4	4	Rajiv 1997: 23	Hist, Med
45	Mankawas-2	28 37 03.7	76 10 21.2	2	New	Hist, Med
46	Mankawas-3	28 37 05.3	76 11 03.3	3	New	Hist, Med
47	Mehara	28 33 47.3	76 09 11.0	1	Rajiv 1997: 25	Hist, Med
48	Noswa	28 26 07.7	76 16 55.7	1	New	Med
49	Pantawas Kalan-1	28 37 42.2	76 12 28.6	2	Rajiv 1997: 26	Med
50	Pantawas Kalan-2	28 39 08.8	76 12 48.3	3	New	Hist, Med
51	Pantawas Khurd	28 39 48.2	76 11 41.9	1	New	EH, MH, LH
52	Ramalwas	28 29 42.8	76 07 31.4	1	New	Hist, Med
53	Rashiwas-1	28 40 37.6	76 08 19.8	2	Rajiv 1997: 29	Med
54	Rashiwas-2	28 39 10.1	76 08 33.0	1	Rajiv 1997: 28	LH, Hist, Med
55	Sahawas-1	28 37 32.7	76 14 41.1	1	Rajiv 1997: 29	Hist, Med
56	Sahawas-2	28 38 42.7	76 13 21.9	2	Rajiv 1997: 29	Med
57	Sarangpur	28 39 09.5	76 02 55.9	2	Rajiv 1997: 28	Hist, Med
58	Siswala	28 33 54.1	76 06 21.6	1	New	Med
59	Tiwala	28 34 12.8	76 07 32.9	9	Rajiv 1997: 30	Hist,

EH= Early Harappan, MH=Mature Harappan, LH=Late Harappan, Hist=Historical, Med=Medieval.

Table 2 showing number of sites of different periods

S.no	Period	No of Sites
1	Early Harappan	02
2	Mature Harappan	02
3	Late Harappan	12
4	Historical	43
5	Medieval	45

Discussion

The antiquity of the study area can be traced back to proto-historic times. Archaeological explorations has revealed that the earliest settlers in the regions belong to Early Harappan culture (Sothi-Siswal culture). So far as not even a single site belongs to Pre-Harappan period (Ghaggar-Hakra/ Hakra culture) has been reported in the area. But in the adjoining area a number of sites of late fourth millennium BCE has been reported (Khatri and Acharya 1995; Rao *et al* 2005; Dangi 2007, 2009; Shinde *et al* 2011).

Sothi-Siswal culture is a regional variant of the Early Harappan culture in the upper and middle Ghaggar basin. Peoples of Early Harappan period use to live in houses of sun dried bricks and fortified towns and villages. They used to wear ornaments of semiprecious stones such as carnelian, agate, jasper, lapis lazuli etc; they were familiar with copper technology. Excavations at Sothi (Dikshit 1984), Banawali (1982) Bhirrana (Rao *et al* 2004; 2005; 2006), Rakhigarhi (Nath 2001), Kalibangan (Lal *et al* 2003) etc. has thrown light on social, economic aspects of this culture. Only two site of this period has been explored in the area under present study. The ceramic assemblages have affinity with the Sothi-Siswal pottery.

The main shapes in this assemblage are jars, vases, bowls, basins and handled pots/basins (Fig 4 & 5). There are variations in size but the formal features are more or less the same. Most of the sherds collected or included in the study are decorated with black bands while the bi-chrome ware is rare in this area. As we move southward in Ghaggar basin, bi-chrome pottery became lesser and lesser. Large scale excavations have been conducted at Farmana (Uesugi, Akinori 2011), Mitathal (Kumar *et al* 2011) and Girawad (Shine *et al* 2011) and in the entire ceramic assemblage of Sothi-Siswal bi-chrome sherds are just one or two. Another site, Manheru is located very near to study area, the site was excavated by M.D. University, Rohtak and University of Delhi, Delhi (Thakaran *et al* 2010:128-159) only a few bi-chrome sherds were recovered during excavations. There are two patterns of the surface decorations; the first one is painted by a broad band from rim to shoulder and in the second case only rim portion is decorated with a black band. In some specimens the former is combined with wavy lines just below the band or with a panel on the body below the shoulder having some geometric designs. The most common geometric designs are hatched triangles, circles and criss-cross lines. In the case of bowls and basins, the inner surface is decorated with comb-incised parallel grooves, either straight or wavy or criss-cross akin to Kalibangan, Fabric-D. Quantity of incised decorated pottery is less as we compare with the sites located near river Ghaggar.

Sothi-Siswal pottery was usually thrown on slow wheel; the rim and neck portion are finished by smoothening with rotation whereas the body portion is finished without rotation as striations and finger impressions of smoothening and scraping are observed on the surface in an irregular way. Usually the wall of the pottery has an uneven thickness. The ring base loop-handled pots are quite common.

Mature Harappan period

Only two sites have yielded remains of Mature Harappan period. Only a few classical Harappan shapes viz. perforated jar, dish-on-stand vases were recovered from the surface (Fig 6). Rohari chert blades are totally absent in this region. Manheru and Mitathal are the two excavated sites in the vicinity of the study area. Mitathal has yielded only one specimen of tan-grey chert where as at Manheru not even a single blade was found. Some sherds akin to Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery were also found from the region. These include bowl, basins and vases (Fig 7). Area under present study is very important to see the relation and interaction of the peoples of the Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture and Harappan civilization. Because Khetri copper mining area was the core area of Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture and this area is situated just southern side of the area of under present study. Quantity of classical Harappan shapes such as perforated jar, long stem dish-on-stand, beakers, painted jars, nail headed bowls and basins are very less on the surface of the sites. First author has conducted extensive explorations in the entire Ghaggar basin and we can conclude that as we move south of the basin quantity of classical Harappan pottery reduces.

Late Harappan Period

The third cultural phase in the proto-history of this region is distinguished by the Late Harappan culture or degenerate phase of urban Harappans. Twelve sites yielded the remains of this phase. The classical Harappan shapes like goblets, perforated jars and classical Harappan paintings fell out of use but some shapes such as beakers, nail headed bowls, dish-on-stands with long stems etc continue with modifications. The common pottery types are dish-on-stands with ribbed junctions, dish-on-stands with broad and short stands, vases with projected undercut rims, jars with wide and narrow mouths, globular vases with flanged rims, beakers with out-turned rims and flasks treated with fine red slip (Fig 8). Out of total 12 Late Harappan sites, 10 were occupied for the first time, two sites of the Mature Harappan period were preferred by the late Harappan peoples in absence of excavation it is difficult to say that whether there is a cultural break between the Harappans and Late Harappans. Mitathal is the only excavated site in the region, there is no cultural break between the Mature Harappan and Late Harappan period. At Mitathal the gradual transformation from Mature Harappan to Late Harappan was observed (Manmohan *et al* 2011). There are two domains of the Late Harappan culture in the Ghaggar basin and the area of both these domains was properly marked with the help of explorations, distribution maps and typological study of the pottery (Dangi 2010: 388; map 6.1; appendix-1) and the area under present study falls in Mitathal-IIB domain.

Historical and Medieval period

Forty three sites of historical period were explored. The number of sites indicated that the after 600 BCE the area under present study was thickly populated as compare to proto-historic period. Note worthy find of this period are two copper coins of Kushana king Vasudeva-I (Fig 9). Common shapes of historical pottery were represented by bowls with incurved rim, carinated cooking *handis*, vases, spouted vases, basins, lid, incense burner. Pottery of later Kushana and Gupta period is less

painted as compare to the pottery of Rangmahal. Naurangabad (Sanger 2005:191-195) and Kokhrakakot (Kumar 1996) were the regional centers during the historical period. Both areas are located very near to the study area.

Forty five sites of medieval period were explored during the survey. Main shapes include sharp edged bowls, vases, pots etc. a few sherds of glazed ware were also collected during the explorations. During the course of explorations we came across a sculpture of Vamana (Fig 10). This sand stone relief measuring 30 x 19 cm shows the quadrimanous pot-bellied dwarfish figure standing in *sambhanga mudra*. The god bears curled locks on the head and wears necklet, necklace, sacred thread, wristlets, bracelets, *kundalas*, anklets and a long *vanamala*. A *srivatsa* (an auspicious symbol) is engraved on the chest. The legs are stumpy and disproportionate to the body. The god holds mace and *chakra* in the rear right and left hands and a conch in the proper left. The conch is placed vertically with spiral-top blow. The normal right hand is held in boon-conferring pose. Behind the head is a round halo with eight petals of lotus carved in it. Brahma and Shiva are carved in top corner. Both sit in *lalitasana* and are four handed. On the lower right is Sankha-Purusha with conch in the left hand and right hand is resting on knee. On the stylistic ground, the image belongs to Gurjara Pratihara period.

Conclusion

Area under present study played a vital role in trade during the proto-historic period. This was the core area for the trade of sand stone and copper artifacts. During the course of explorations more the 300 grinding stone and fragments were recorded on the Harappan sites and some of them were collected for study (Fig 11). Now a days also village Kaliana is famous for kitchen stone objects such as grinding stones, saddle querns, passels etc. (fig). Kaliana hill stone has a sugary texture, red pink to pinkish grey in colour and is criss-crossed with thin hematite and quartz filled fractures. This is the typical feature of stone objects of Kalia hills (Law 2011:119). One major aim of present explorations was to identify work shop of Harappan period around Kaliana hills, but we were unable to locate any such place. So far as we think modern development activities and pressure of agriculture led them vanished. Many sites of Harappan period are located near source of sand stone (Fig 3). First author has conducted extensive explorations the Ghaggar plains and notices such types of stone objects in abundance at 89 sites, some sites which of them are given here Mitathal, Kunghar, Farmana, Farmana-3, Girawad, Siswal, Madina-2, Kheri Meham, Rakhigarh, Balu, Burj, Bhirrana, Banawali, Sothi, Kalibangan, Baror etc. Khetri copper mines are located 45 km south of the study area. These mines are the main source of copper during the Harappan period (Agrawal 2000, Law 2011). During the third millennium BCE peoples Ganeshwar-Jodhpura culture was settled around Khetri copper belt. Ganeshwar-Jodhpura type pottery (Fig 7 & 8) was noticed on the Harappan sites of area under present study, indicates that there was a connection between both these cultures. Lead and Tin is also available in Tosham hills and it is proved now that these deposits were used by Harappans (Kochhar *et al* 1999, Awasthi *et al* 1981, Law 2011).

The researchers conducted extensive village-to-village survey in the region and recorded sites with the help of GPS, besides size of settlements and other vital information. This has helped us to correct the earlier recording of sites and there. Recently some scholars surveyed various parts of Haryana addressing this problem (Dangi 2007, 2009a, 2009b, 2010, 2011; Singh *et al* 2010 and 2011). Future researchers shall have data on which they can easily bank upon.

Most of the archaeological sites are either converted into the agriculture fields or the soil is removed for development purpose. The situation is very grim because in a few years it will be very difficult for the archaeologists to spot any site for excavation. Even today it is very hard to spot an intact mound. Hence the present study has its own importance as the sites are now recorded for posterity which may not exist in future.

Acknowledgements

It is my pleasant duty to acknowledge many individuals who enlightened me during my research work such as Profs. Manmohan Kumar, Dr. R.S. Bisht, Shri G.B. Sharma. for their support, valuable suggestions and encouragement. I am grateful to Dr. J.S Kharakwal and Dr. P.P. Joglekar for his keen interest in my research work. I owe sincere thanks to Dr. Akinori Uesugi, for providing me technical support. I am grateful to my friends Nishant Dhankar, Manujeet Nandal, Sudhir, Manjeet Nandal, Samunder Hooda and Manish Gulia who provided us constant help during the field survey.

References

- Agrawal, D.P. 2000. *Ancient Metal Technology and Archaeology of South Asia*. Aryan books International, New Delhi
- Awasthi, S.C., M. Parsad, V.K. Anand. 1981. Geology, structure and sulphide mineralisation of Tosham, District Bhiwani, Haryana. *Records of Geological Survey of India* 112(2):7-16
- Bisht, R.S. 1982. Excavations at Banawali: 1974-77, in *Harappan Civilization: A Contemporary Perspective* (G.L. Possehl Eds), Oxford & IBH Publishing Co., New Delhi.
- Dangi, Vivek 2011. Explorations along with River Ghaggar and *Sirhind Nala* (Haryana and Punjab). In *Man and Environment* XXXVI(2):66-87

- Dangi, Vivek 2010; *A Study of Proto-Historic settlements in Upper Ghaggar Basin*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Rohtak: Maharshi Dayanad University.
- Dangi, Vivek 2009a. *Archaeology of Ghaggar Basin: Settlement Archaeology of Meham Block, district Rohtak, Haryana, India, Occasional Paper 7: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past*. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Dangi, Vivek 2009b. Recent explorations in the Chautang Basin (Jind District, Haryana), in *Occasional Paper 9: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past* (T.Osada and Akinori Uesugi Eds) pp 73-163. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Dangi, Vivek 2007. Recent Exploration in Meham, District Rohtak', Haryana. In *Puratattva No. 37:205-212*.
- Dangi, Vivek, 2006, *Settlement Pattern of Meham Block District Rohtak*. M.Phil. Dissertation. Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University.
- Dikshit, K.N. (1984). 'The Sothi Complex: Old Records and Fresh Observation', in B.B. Lal and S.P. Gupta (Eds) *Frontiers of the Indus Civilization*, Books and Books, New Delhi
- Grover, S.P. and Ramesh Kumar 1980. Geology and Structure of Tosham and Baradari Hill, Tosham, Haryana . In *Publication of the Central of Advance Study in Geology* no. 12:219-236, Chandigarh, Punjab University.
- Haryana district Gazetteers, Bhiwani* 1982
- Kochhar, N, R. Kochar and D.K. Chakrabarti 1999. A new Source of Primary Tin Ore in the Indus Civilization. *South Asian Studies* 15:115-118
- Kumar, Manmohan 1996. Ancient Mint at Rohtak. In K.K. Maheswari and Biswajeet Path (eds.) *Numismatic Panorama* Harman Publish House, New Delhi.
- Kumar, Manmohan 2009. Harappan Settlements in the Ghaggar-Yamuna Divide, in *Occasional Paper 7: Linguistics, Archaeology and the Human Past* (T. Osada and Akinori Uesugi Eds.) pp 1-78. Kyoto: Indus Project.
- Lal, B.B., J.P. Joshi, B.K. Thapar and Madhu Bala (2003). *MASI no. 98 Excavations at Kalibangan: The Early Harappans (1961-1969)*, New Delhi.
- Law, Randall William 2011. *Inter-Regional Interactions and Urbaism in the Ancient Indus Valley: A Geologic Provenience Study of Harappan's Rock and Mineral Assemblage*, Kyoto, Japan, Indus Project.
- Manmohan Kumar, Akinori Uesugi, V.Shinde, Vivek Dangi, Vijay Kumar, Rajeev Maan and Arun Singh 2011. Excavations at Mitathal, District Bhiwani (Haryana) 2010-11: A Preliminary Report. In *Puratattva* No.41:168-178.
- Nath, A, 2001. Rakhigarhi: 1999-2000, in *Puratattva* no.31: 43-46.
- Rajiv 1997, *Archaeology and History of Dadri Block-II (District Bhiwani)*, Unpublished M.Phil. Dissertation, Maharshi Dayanad University, Rohtak, Haryana.
- Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, Samir Diwan and U.A. Shastry 2005. New Light on the Excavation of Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana, *Puratattva* 35: 60-68.
- Rao, L.S., N.B. Sahu, Prabash Sahu, U.A. Shastry and Samir Diwan 2004. Unearthing Harappan Settlement at Bhirrana, *Puratattva* 34: 20-24.
- Rao, L.S., Nandhani. B. Sahu, U.A. Shastry Prabash Sahu and Samir Diwan 2006. Bhirrana Excavations-2005-06, *Puratattva* 36: 45-49.
- Sanger, P.B.S. 2005. Excavations at Naurangabad-Haryana (2000-01), *Puratattva* 35:191-195
- Singh, R.N., C.A. Petrie, V. Pawar, A.K. Pandey, S.Neogi, M.Singh, A.K. Singh, D. Parik and C. Lancelotti 2010. Changing Patterns of Settlements in the Rise and Fall of Harappan Urbanism and Beyond: a Preliminary Report on the Rakhigarhi Hinterland Survey 2009, *Man and Environment XXXV*(1):37-53).
- Singh, R.N., C.A. Petrie, V.Pawar, A.K.Pandey and D. Parikh 2011. New Light onto Settlement along the river Ghaggar and its Hinterland: A Preliminary Report on the Ghaggar Hinterland Survey 2010, *Man and Environment XXXVI*(2):88-106

Suraj Bhan, 1972, *Prehistoric Archaeology of the Saraswati and Drishadvati Valley(Haryana)*. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, M.S. University Baroda.

Suraj Bhan 1975. *Excavation at Mitathal (1968) and other Exploration in Sutlej-Yamuna Divide*. Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University Press.

Thakran, R.C., Amar Singh, Narender and Vikas 2010. Excavations on Manheru 2009 and Explorations in its Environs, District Bhiwani, Haryana. *Aitihya* 1:128-159.

Uesugi, Akinori 2011. Pottery from Settlement Area, in *Excavations at Farmana, District Rohtak, Haryana, India 2006-2008* (Vasant Shinde, Toshiki Osada and Manmohan Kumar Eds). Kyoto: Indus Project.

Key to Figures

Fig 1. Map showing location of the study area

Fig 2. Map showing explored sites with major excavated sites

Fig 3. Map showing distribution of proto-historic sites and hill

Fig 4. Early Harappan pottery

Fig 5. Early Harappan Pottery

Fig 6. Mature Harappan Pottery

Fig 7. Ganeshwar-Jodhpura pottery recovered from study area

Fig 8 Late Harappan Pottery

Fig 9. Copper coins of Kushana ruler Vasudeva-I

Fig 10. Sandstone sculpture of Vamana

Fig 11. Stone objects